

A CRITICAL REVIEW OF THE CHALLENGES OF REAL ESTATE INVESTMENT FOR BUSINESSES INVESTING IN UGANDA'S REAL ESTATE

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Abstract

The 2021 Statistics Report from the Uganda Bureau of Statistics showed that real estate investments in Uganda in the year 2021 contributed 6.3% to the Gross Domestic Product and 7.8% to the employment opportunities of the country. Despite this significant role, businesses encounter several challenges hindering their efforts to speedily and successfully invest in real estate in Uganda. These challenges that exist include: lack of the provision and availability of expensive serviced land for real estate investment; lack of real estate investment strategy, analysis and management skills; poor real estate investment decisions; inadequate regulatory policy for real estate investment planning and development; expensive real estate finance and lack of real estate financing skills; outdated land and property laws; and existence of a weak professional body monitoring real estate investment professionals. This phenomenon is a cause for a number of real estate developments that are not well conceptualized, business financial losses and bankruptcy due to bad real estate investment decision making and poorly performing real estate investments; evident in the high levels of vacant spaces which according to a 2022 Report by Stanbic Properties averages at 11% for Grade B and 26% for Grade C Buildings. The overall aim of the study was then to conduct a critical review of these challenges from the perspective of the businesses themselves to inform decision making and policy through a multi-dimensional analysis of Uganda's real estate investment environment, utilizing survey methods that included literature review, interviews, and questionnaires with primary data being collected using quantitative research methods while secondary data being obtained from the review of relevant literature and documents. A sample size of 260 real estate businesses out of the estimated 800 was drawn to participate in the quantitative study to meet acceptable and reliable outcomes for the study by allowing only a 5% margin of error in the results of the study and confidence level of 95%. Data analysis was based on the mean score values of the identified challenges as given by the respondents prioritizing challenges that weighted the most significance and thereafter conducting statistical testing by grouping and assigning values to responses through ranking and order statistics. The study revealed that the highest rated concerns for businesses as key challenges in the existing real estate investment strategy formulation, analysis, decision-making, environment and processes originated from: (i) the unpredictable changes in the property market arising from market volatility, (ii) Uncertainty and the limited access to reliable and update property data prices, rental rates, market trends, (iii) Corruption tendencies in the land administration system, and (iv) the land title acquisition challenges. The research recommends the development of a strategic framework for real estate investment that emphasizes improved access to reliable property data and metrics to facilitate benchmarking across residential, commercial, industrial, and hospitality segments. Further, policy makers will look at the real estate gaps highlighted to craft policy interventions that fully address the needs of businesses and the various stakeholders for sustainable development.

Keywords: Real Estate, Decision-Making, Investing, Real Estate Challenges, Uganda's Real Estate.

1. INTRODUCTION

Uganda's Real Estate Sector continues to present significant opportunities for businesses to invest and capitalize on the country's economic growth and urbanization which according to the World Bank (2025: 1), UN-Habitat (2023: 1) and Uganda's Ministry of Finance, Planning and Economic Development (2024: 4) shows a very strong positive growth trend being driven in part by huge infrastructure investments and the commencement of oil production but also by the major demographic and developmental trend towards Vision 2030. The confluence of these macroeconomic and demographic forces is currently what is creating a high-demand environment for Uganda's Real Estate particularly in the residential and commercial properties in and around major urban centers like Kampala, Wakiso, Entebbe, Mbarara and Jinja (Newport International Journal, 2024: 1). In the year 2021, real estate investments in Uganda contributed 6.3% to the GDP and 7.8% to the employment opportunities of the country (Uganda Bureau of Statistics 2021: 110). Despite this significant role, businesses have encountered several challenges that hinder their efforts to speedily and successfully invest in real estate ranging from lack of skills in real estate investment strategy formulation, analysis and decision-making according to reports by Knight Frank Uganda (2023: 1) and Kalema and Kayiira (2008: 18). This phenomenon is a cause for a number of real estate developments that are not well conceptualized, evident in the high levels of vacant spaces averaging at 11% for Grade B and 26% for Grade C Buildings (Stanbic Properties Limited 2022: 4). This paper critically reviews Real Estate Investment for Businesses Investing in Uganda's Real Estate Sector focusing on the identification of the real challenges that exist as identified by the businesses themselves. Findings of this study and review will promote quality real estate investment and growth as it makes known these challenges that need to be addressed by businesses and policy makers including other players such as the real estate association bodies to ensure improved real estate decision making, well prepared real estate investing businesses and crafting of much needed policy interventions. The work also forms part of the contribution to strengthening real estate education in Uganda towards a more professionalized real estate sector.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Global and Regional Perspectives on Real Estate Markets

Estimates by Savills (2021:15) place the global real estate market value at approximately US\$326 trillion in 2020, surpassing global equities and debt securities combined underscoring its importance to businesses, investors and policy makers alike not only in capital accumulation but also as a key driver of macroeconomic stability. Cross-border investment in real estate exceeded US\$400 billion in 2019 before COVID-19 disruptions (MSCI, 2020:12) with investors remaining wary of frontier markets due to institutional and currency risks that often characterise such markets (Baum, 2015:66).

Moreover, contrary to the real estate markets in emerging markets that are still immature and facing challenges of tenure insecurity, limited access to finance, and weak regulatory enforcement (Keivani and Werna, 2001:57), the real estate markets in developed economies such as the United States, the United Kingdom, Germany, and Japan exhibit high levels of

maturity according to Ling and Archer (2017:41) and Pagliari (2017:23) and have benefited from a strong legal frameworks, high levels of market transparency, standardized valuation practices, transparent land administration, and well-developed deep mortgage financing systems that have seen real estate growth in those countries much more organized, financed and more profitable.

Within in the East African Community (EAC), the real estate market continues to experience rapid growth due to a number of factors that could includes among others: the rapid urbanization, rising middle-class incomes, demographic growth, and infrastructure investments (UN-Habitat, 2014:72). The 2020 UN-Habitat Report on urbanisation shows sub-Saharan Africa as having one of the fastest urbanization rates globally, with an urban population projected to reach 1.5 billion by 2050 (UN-Habitat, 2020:17). This rapid growth fuels demand for residential and commercial real estate.

Uganda's real estate market in comparison reflects both the opportunities of a rapidly urbanizing population and the constraints of tenure insecurity and inadequate regulatory frameworks with the real estate bill still in progress and yet to be passed into an Act of Parliament. The Uganda Bureau of Statistics (UBOS) Data shows Kampala, Uganda's capital, as facing housing deficit exceeding 2.1 million units, with demand projected to rise further due to population growth (UBOS, 2020:19). This presents opportunities for real estate in housing investment but limited mortgage penetration (below 1% of GDP) restricts access to long-term financing according to a report by the Bank of Uganda (2019:12) and therefore much needed capital to support business tap into the real estate investment opportunities is not readily available and/or very expensive to acquire.

2.2. Empirical Studies on Real Estate Development in Uganda

Several literatures from Kamulegeya, (2017:23), UBOS (2020:56), Goodfellow (2017:68) and Knight Frank (2019:14) on the performance of the real estate market in Uganda shows significant growth experienced over the past two decades, primarily driven by rapid urbanization, a growing middle class, diaspora remittances, population growth averaging over 3% annually, increased demand for commercial and residential real estate space as well as increased investment. This has intensified pressures on land and property markets, fuelling both formal and informal real estate developments (Kamulegeya, 2017:23).

The emergency and growth seen in a growing middle class with increased disposable income has stimulated demand for modern housing, retail, and office space, particularly in metropolitan areas and neighbourhoods of Kyanja, Nalya, Kira, Entebbe, etc., according to a 2019 report by the Knight Frank (2019:14). Additionally, local and foreign investment flows into construction (such as seen with VAAL Real Estate and Cananze Estates), mortgage financing (that has broadened to even unregistered land by most of the major Commercial Banks), and property development have strengthened the sector, making it a key contributor to GDP and a preferred asset class for wealth preservation.

Despite these positive trends, scholars note that the real estate market in Uganda remains underdeveloped, characterized by informality, tenure disputes, limited financing options,

inadequate infrastructure, complex land tenure systems, high land values, inconsistent application of valuation methods and practices and high construction costs (Kamulegeya, 2017:25; MLHUD, 2013:17 and Kayiira, 2014:212).

Financial institutions remain cautious in extending mortgages due to high interest rates and limited credit history among potential borrowers (World Bank, 2019:54). At the same time, speculative investment in land has contributed to escalating property prices in Kampala and other urban centers according to Goodfellow (2010:99) and with no property tax on vacant land in site, speculators can continue to hold land indefinitely thereby making inaccessible prime real estate locations that would otherwise attract many willing businesses and investors. Nkurunziza (2007:27) underscores the prevalence of informal land delivery systems in Kampala, which, while providing land access for low-income groups, undermines planned development and leads to unregulated settlements. Mugambwa (2007:145) further notes that tenure insecurity, especially under customary and mailo regimes, creates barriers for large-scale real estate projects.

Nonetheless, Uganda's real estate industry remains one of the most dynamic in East Africa, positioned as both a driver and beneficiary of the country's broader economic transformation (Knight Frank, 2019:15).

2.3. Real Estate Market Data Opaqueness and Uncertainty in Uganda

To critically review the challenges that business must navigate while undertaking investment decisions in Uganda's real estate sector, it is important to appreciate the nature of the real estate market data that businesses ought to rely on while undertaking real estate investment decisions as this provides context and rationale for the decision undertaken. According to Gonza et al. (2024: 278), the availability, quality and depth of real estate market data across the different segments and coverage of geographies, real estate sectors and types of data continue to pose a challenge for businesses investing in Uganda's real estate. Moreover, the 2024 Global Real Estate Transparency Index (GRETI), scored Uganda's real estate market information as being opaque and inefficient (JLL and LaSalle, 2024: 23). GRETI measures real estate transparency among property markets using six indicators of: investment performance, market fundamentals, listed vehicles, regulatory and legal framework, transaction processes, and sustainability.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This is an applied research study that blends qualitative and quantitative approaches to solve real-world problems as it sits at the intersection of theory and practice. The research philosophy for this study is therefore a pragmatic research philosophy allowing a flexible integration of qualitative and quantitative methods by combining methods from both the positivism and interpretivism philosophies to address practical problems in real estate investment (Creswell, 2014: 23) as well as encouraging a focus on real-world relevance and stakeholder perspectives, which are essential for understanding contextual challenges in Uganda's real estate sector (Johnson & Christensen, 2019: 78). A purely positivist (quantitative) stance would risk only

focusing on measurable financial and economic indicators (such as interest rates, yields, GDP, inflation) while ignoring social, institutional, and contextual realities like corruption and land tenure complexities, or even the business culture in Uganda. Conversely, adopting a purely interpretivist (qualitative) stance may only capture perceptions and narratives but lack the empirical rigor to generalize the findings. The interplay of both positivist (quantitative) and interpretivist (qualitative) philosophies evident in pragmatic research philosophy then becomes critical.

3.1. Research process and design

The research process started with the identification and selection of the problem following theoretical knowledge accumulation which was then reinforced with a review of literature to map theoretical foundations and existing gaps as guided by Creswell (2014:32) resulting into a reformulation and refinement of the research problem to inform the potential design of the study. The research objective and question was then framed to guide the inquiry, supported by a pragmatic philosophy that allowed mixed methods integration (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019:144). Due to the variability of the information needed to address the different aspects of the research question, and the perceived limitations of each research method, it was necessary to use multiple data collection methods (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 1998). The convergent parallel mixed-method approach or triangulation of methods, was preferred to obtain as much information as possible from different sources particularly relevant in Uganda, where land administration and real estate development involve not only measurable economic and financial dynamics but also deeply embedded socio-cultural and institutional factors. The mixed model was adopted to facilitate triangulation and complementarity of research results.

Quantitative methods were employed to measure perceptions and attitudes towards the challenges in the existing real estate investment strategy formulation, analysis, decision making, environment and processes for Businesses investing in Uganda's real estate using Likert-scale questionnaires. As Joshi et al. (2015:132) argue, the Likert scale is one of the most reliable tools for measuring attitudes and behaviours, provided potential biases in response styles are considered.

This allowed for the systematic collection of data from a broad sample of businesses, stakeholders, including property owners, developers, and land administrators. The study has employed a descriptive research design to agree on the identification of challenges in the existing real estate investment strategy formulation, analysis, decision-making, environment and processes for businesses in Uganda. This approach helped to ensure objectivity, rigor, and logical reasoning, and eliminated any potential sources of bias.

Data was collected through surveys, interviews, and secondary sources, and analyzed using both statistical and thematic approaches (Bryman, 2016:384). Findings were synthesized to construct a practical critical review of the challenges of real estate investment for businesses in Uganda (Kothari, 2004:223). The process concludes with recommendations for business practice and policy in Uganda's real estate sector.

3.2. Sample Size and Selection

This study employed random sampling techniques for selection of respondents to ensure a good representation of the views of the businesses in the different location. Purposive sampling (Hanlon and Larget 2011: 1) as well as stratified sampling was used to select relevant respondents for the interview who were mainly individuals with expertise and experience in the real estate sector such as heads of credit in commercial banks, Valuers involved in valuations of real estate, Agents and Brokers from the Association of Real Estate Agents, and officials from MoLHUD. The study targeted the following:

Using the formula adopted from Krejcie and Morgan (1970:607), a sample size of 260 real estate businesses out of 800 was drawn to participate in the study. This sample size met acceptable and reliable outcomes for the study by allowing only a 5% margin of error in the results of the study and confidence level of 95% as per the formula below

$$S = \frac{X^2 N P(1 - P)}{d^2(N - 1) + X^2 P(1 - P)}$$

Where: ($X^2 = 3.841$ (chi-square value for 95% confidence, degree of freedom (df) =1), $N = 800$ (population),

$P = 0.5$ (population proportion), $d = 0.05$ (margin of error = 5%)).

A total of 196 questionnaires were distributed to businesses involved in real estate in Uganda to get their views on the main research question of this study while a total of 64 questionnaires were distributed to the land officials, valuers, real estate agents and brokers as well as the staff of secured lending commercial banks making a total of 260.

3.3. Quantitative Data Analysis

Two methods of descriptive statistics i.e., weighted mean score (M) and standard deviation (SD) were employed. Using the 5-point Likert scale that was used to collect the data and as well establish the relevance of each indicator in the construct, the weighted mean score and standard deviation of each variable were determined. Weighted mean score in the study entailed allocating a point to the respondent's ratings of the variables, e.g., extremely important equals 5 points, and not so important equals 1 point. And while the weighted mean score has been used extensively in research with similar variables (Likert data), determining the rank can be tricky when dealing with multiple indicators with the same mean value. In this instance, the standard deviation of each factor is considered alongside the mean value which would then allow factors with a more minor standard to be given a higher rank, as they are considered more consistent. The data was then analysed based on the mean score values of the identified challenges as given by the respondents. More so, in prioritizing the challenges that weighted the most significance, the researcher based on their significance levels; the scale of 1-5 interval and the mean score range interpretation proposed by Li, Ng and Skitmore (2013: 7), Joshi et al. (2015:132) and Boone and Boone (2012:2) was adopted as follows: “Strongly Disagree” (1), “Disagree” (2), “Not Sure” (3), “Agree” (4) and “Strongly Agree” (5) and the computations of the means on the basis of responses that either agree or disagree with these challenges. Analysis

of data was done through statistical testing using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS®) Version 29), the latest software version used to analyse quantitative data by grouping and assigning values to responses from the survey through ranking and order statistics. Presentation and display of data was by use of tables, pie charts and bar graphs supported with Microsoft Power BI.

The weighted mean score was calculated for each construct using SPSS based on the underlying formula:

$$\text{Weighted Mean Score} = \frac{\sum 1n_1 + 2n_2 + 3n_3 + 4n_4 + 5n_5}{[n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + n_4 + n_5]}$$

Where: (n_1 = number of respondents who strongly disagree, n_2 = number of respondents who disagree, n_3 = number of respondents not sure, n_4 = number of respondents who agree, and n_5 = number of respondents who strongly agree).

3.4. Qualitative Analysis

Coding and categorization were conducted for analysis, followed by written interpretation of the findings as a form of presentation and display of data in its qualitative nature (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2014:72). Some of the qualitative data obtained through the questionnaires was converted to quantitative data using a Likert scale and subsequently analyzed through statistical techniques already described above (Creswell, 2014:203). Secondary data from relevant documents, reports, and literature was subjected to content analysis by systematically organizing and synthesizing the information to generate meaningful conclusions (Kothari, 2004:223).

4. PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

4.1. Challenges related to RE Investment Analysis and Decision-making

Respondents were asked to give their opinions on challenges related to RE investment analysis and decision making. The data referenced for analysis are based on the mean score values of the 11 identified challenges related to RE investment analysis and decision making.

From Figure 2 below, we can see that:

Unpredictable changes in the property market arising from market volatility and uncertainty and the limited access to reliable and update property data prices, rental rates, market trends came out as the highest rated concerns for businesses. With both challenges scoring more than 4.2, these were viewed as critical challenges for businesses when undertaking investment analysis and decision making for RE investments.

Strongly agreeing with unpredictable changes in the property market (mean score of 4.32) could be a reflection of RE market volatility due to inflation, interest rate shifts, and political uncertainty.

As one of the experts that was interviewed from the Association of Real Estate Agents in Uganda (AREA) intimated, *“There is general desire by the real estate market to price in US Dollars as opposed to pricing in Uganda Shillings to hedge the inflation risks associated with the Uganda Shillings.”*

Similarly, unforeseen economic events (such as COVID-19) have significant impacts to businesses that most respondents rated it with a mean score of 4.25 highlighting it as a critical concern for businesses due to its impact on business health.

The high mean score for limited access to reliable and update property data prices, rental rates and market trends point to the opaqueness of real estate market and the risk that businesses attach to this risk in Uganda. Indeed Gonza et al. (2024:278) highlights the necessity of making real estate investment decisions in the face of uncertainty as becoming an integral part of all businesses that seek to invest in real estate in Uganda due to market data opaqueness.

Businesses investing in Uganda’s RE sector must contend with the fact that; accurate rental rates, land values, and market trends are either hard to obtain or outdated in most of the cases therefore requiring strategic action to properly inform a RE investment.

Challenges related to RE Investment Analysis & Decision Making	Mean Score
Unpredictable changes in the property market arising from market volatility and uncertainty	4.32
Unforeseen economic events such as COVID19, economic downturns	4.25
Limited access to reliable and update property data prices, rental rates, market trends	4.18
Market selection and location risk related to wrong choice of property location	4.10
Overestimation of rental incomes arising from poor vacancy projections, maintenance costs	3.95
Information asymmetry	3.91
Under estimation of expenses such as insurance, management, unexpected repairs	3.88
Insufficient market knowledge particularly local economic conditions, supply and demand	3.82
Limited capacity to develop a strategy for investment in real estate	3.76
Poor quality of property valuations that guide sale or purchase of real estate	3.69
Land tenure complexities	3.55

Figures 1: Heat Map and Mean Scores of the 11 Challenges related to RE investment analysis and decision making

4.2.Challenges related to RE Investment Environment

Respondents were also asked to give their opinions on challenges related to the RE Environment. From figure 3 below, it can be seen that businesses identified; (i) Corruption tendencies in the land administration system, (ii) Security and safety concerns as well as (iii) Interest rates and financing costs all of them with a mean score higher than 4.2 as being of greatest concern and high risk to businesses as regards to RE environment. With each of these challenges, more than 80% of the businesses either agreed or strongly agreed pointing to these challenges as being significant structural barriers, discouraging real estate investment and inflating costs for businesses seeking to invest in Uganda's real estate environment.

There is a lot of literature that seems to agree with these findings. According to Transparency International (2011: 12) and the Anti-Corruption Resource Centre (2015: 5) the land sector is particularly vulnerable to corrupt practices due to the high value of land, weak land governance structures, and lack of transparency in land transactions. Bribery is mostly seen in the form of corruption in land administration, where officials demand illicit payments for services that should be free or expedited (Rose-Ackerman, 1999: 91). According to a World Bank Report (2013: 67) citizens in many developing countries are often made to pay bribes to secure land titles, permits, or to avoid unlawful evictions. Equally, a study conducted by Moyo (2013: 34) in Sub-Saharan Africa found that nearly 60% of land transactions involved informal payments, reinforcing systemic corruption. It is no surprise that businesses identified this factor as being among the greatest top three concerns as regards the RE investment environment in Uganda.

Other corruption tendencies in land administration processes are evident in fraudulent land documentation, including fake land titles and forged ownership records, (Toulmin and Quan, 2000: 112). The cancelling of over 1200 Land Titles by governments according to online sources which exercised coincided with the same time this study was being conducted only worked to reinforce the great risk/concern that businesses could have expressed by either agreeing or strongly agreeing with this particular challenge that was posed to them during the study. Mean score ratings between 3.5 and 4.0 points to systemic inefficiencies and transitional challenges that businesses investing in real estate have highlighted as regards environment related challenges that require urgent attention.

Challenges relating to RE environment with mean scores less than 3.5 such as:

- a. access to diverse financing options could point to a lack of awareness on alternative financing options available in real estate such as REITs or Public Private Financing. Most businesses are majorly familiar with traditional borrowing from commercial banks and using personal (equity) financing.
- b. Environmental concerns such as disasters, climate change, sustainability requirements which while developers acknowledge the challenge, few are actually embedding it in their building designs perhaps explaining why not many businesses see it as a strong concern for them with the repercussions being seen in developments that are increasingly being flooded whenever there are flush floods (UNDP, 2023; Cost Uganda, 2020).

Challenges related to RE Environment	Mean Score
Access to diverse financing options	3.40
Corruption tendencies in the land administration	4.50
Environmental concerns such as disasters, climate change, sustainability requirements	3.50
Interest rates and financing costs	4.30
Market oversaturation arising from over supply a certain property type	3.20
Political instability and policy shifts	4.10
Regulatory changes (that impact zoning, land use)	4.00
Security and safety concerns	4.40
Taxation policies (e.g. VAT, Landlord Act)	3.70
Technology obsolescence that renders a property almost useless after a few years	3.90

Figures 2: Mean Scores of the responses to the 10 Challenges related to RE Environment

4.3. Challenges related to RE Investment Processes

Respondents were also asked to give their opinions on challenges related to the RE Investment Process.

From figure 4 below referenced for analysis, It is seen from the mean scores that respondents recorded high concerns in the land title acquisition processes with a mean score of 4.4 for over 80% of the respondents. This points to challenges in acquiring land titles in Uganda perceived as being too costly and slow with corruption-prone procedures at land offices that are considered understaffed with poor logistics according to reports by USAID (2018:22) and UBOS (2023:33).

The average cost of titling a small plot of land measuring approximately 11 decimals in Uganda—including survey, approval, and registration fees—can exceed UGX 2 million when informal payments are factored in. Respondents identified this as a major challenge requiring urgent strategic intervention (MLHUD, 2020:11).

Even when the business has acquired a title, there are sometimes cases where the acquired title is contested which according to the New Vision (2025:4) is largely due to double titling and unclear land boundaries resulting from inadequate field verification and weak enforcement of cadastral standards.

Businesses also highlighted great concern with delays in approval of investment plans with a mean score of 4.20.

The concurrence by most businesses on challenges related to getting investment approvals is in consonance with the Uganda Investment Authority report of 2022 which indicated that the bureaucracy and red tape in government processes means that Investors often have to navigate multiple government agencies, each requiring separate approvals, causing extended processing timelines (UIA, 2022:17).

Challenges related to RE Investment Processes	Mean Rating
Delays in approval of investment plans	4.20
Framework for land delivery for investment purposes	4.00
Land title acquisition (expensive, cumbersome)	4.40
Negotiation & purchase (price, contingencies, legal terms)	3.60
Property identification & due diligence	3.70

Figure 3: Mean Scores of the responses to the 5 Challenges related to RE Investment Processes

It can as well be seen from the results in Figure 4 above that the land delivery framework is another systemic issue, exacerbated by unclear ownership patterns and inconsistent land access policies.

The legal recognition of dual interests in land under the mailo tenure where by either party (the owner and the tenant by occupancy) cannot make decision on land without consulting the other, has affected the real estate market in Uganda with businesses being required not only to engage the title owner, but also the different individuals in physical occupancy of the land (who by the way might be very different from the title owner) before they commit resources and make a final decision to purchase the land.

This problem between the land lord and tenant by occupancy according to Oryema (2016: 27) is so intense that political and legal land reform efforts such as the Land Reform Decree of 1975, The Constitution of 1995, the Land Act of 1998 and the Land Policy of 2012 have attempted to address the issue of dual interests on mailo land, with limited success.

This duality and multi-layered structure of land ownership undoubtedly makes land transactions and land delivery mechanisms for investment land very risky often requiring a lot of ground information and detailed background checks which are expensive for businesses and yet themselves not a full proof.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of the study indicate that *unpredictable changes in the property market arising from market volatility and uncertainty and the limited access to reliable and update property data prices, rental rates, market trends* are the greatest concerns for businesses in the existing real estate investment strategy formulation, analysis and decision-making

Furthermore, the findings indicate that (i) *corruption tendencies in the land administration system*, (ii) *security and safety concerns as well as* (iii) *Interest rates and financing costs* form the greatest concern as regards to RE environment, being significant structural barriers, discouraging real estate investment and inflating costs for businesses seeking to invest in Uganda's real estate environment. Securing a loan from Ugandan Banks is still very expensive across the board with the situation being worse if a business secures a loan from money lenders and micro-finance. The lowest interest rates are around 18% per annum going high as much as close to 50% per annum. There is however government efforts in cubbing down these rates through lowering of the Central Bank Lending Rates (CBR) and sanctions for money lenders but the situation is yet to improve for borrowers.

Similarly, government efforts towards a fully automated and digitized land register continues to be seen but challenges of corruption in the land administration system still persist for businesses that seek either to transfer a particular piece of real estate or conduct a survey and title a certain piece of real estate with the processes often dodged in delays without a clear turnaround time for a particular transaction. This impacts significantly on real estate investment decisions and the property market in Uganda in general thereby acting as a disincentive for Uganda's business environment.

It is recommended that businesses develop a strategic framework for real estate investment emphasizing improved access to reliable property data and metrics to facilitate benchmarking across residential, commercial and industrial.

6. CONTRIBUTIONS TO KNOWLEDGE AND POLICY

With hindsight that research in this field is still limited, this study will go a long way to contribute to the general knowledge of real estate investment strategy formulation, decision-making and analysis in Uganda for the various stakeholders in the academia and other institutions to improve and measure outcomes of the decisions in the real estate market and more so the real estate investment to enable sustainable development.

The findings and recommendations of this research will as well be important in providing guidance to policy makers and implementers in the field of real estate investment/development in Uganda. The policy makers will get to know the challenges in the existing real estate investment strategy formulation, analysis, decision-making, environment and processes for businesses in Uganda to support the crafting of interventions required to address these challenges. This will guide the policy makers when undertaking real estate policy formulation that looks at the gaps and ensure the policy addresses identified challenges fully to meet the needs of businesses and the various stakeholders for sustainable development.

References

- 1) Baum, A., 2015. *Global property investment: Strategies, structures, decisions*. 2nd ed. London: Routledge.
- 2) Boone, H.N. and Boone, D.A. 2012. Analysing Likert data. *Journal of Extension*, 50(2), pp.1–5.
- 3) Bryman, A., 2016. *Social Research Methods*. 5th ed. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- 4) Cost Uganda (2020) ‘Climate Change versus Infrastructure in Uganda, a call for concerted efforts in infrastructure development’, *Cost Uganda*. Available at: <https://www.cost.or.ug/2020/05/25/climate-change-versus-infrastructure-in-uganda-a-call-for-concerted-efforts-in-infrastructure-development/> (Accessed: 14 March 2025).
- 5) Creswell, J.W. 2014. *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. 4th ed. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- 6) Gonza, A., Chikafalimani, S. H. P. and Kibwami, N. 2024. Decision Theory: Analysing decision-making processes of businesses investing in real estate in Uganda -A literature review. *The Seybold Report*, 19 (10): 237-287.
- 7) Goodfellow, T. (2017) ‘Urban fortunes and skeleton cityscapes: real estate and late urbanization in Kampala and Kigali’, *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, 41(5), pp. 786-803.
- 8) Hanlon B., and Larget B. 2011. *Samples and Populations*. Madison.: University of Wisconsin, .
- 9) Haradhan M. 2017. Two Criteria for Good Measurements in Research: Validity and Reliability. Chittagong, Bangladesh.: Premier University. Retrieved September 13 May 2020, 2022, from <https://mpru.unimuenchen.de/83458>.
- 10) Johnson, B. and Christensen, L., 2019. *Educational research: Quantitative, qualitative, and mixed approaches*. 6th ed. Thousand Oaks: Sage, p. 78.
- 11) Joshi, A., Kale, S., Chandel, S. and Pal, D.K. (2015) *Likert Scale: Explored and Explained*. *British Journal of Applied Science & Technology*, 7(4), pp. 396–403
- 12) Kalema, W. S. and Kayiira, D. 2008. *Access To Housing Finance In Africa: Exploring The Issues*. Kampala: FinMark Trust.
- 13) Kayiira, D. 2014. *Land Administration Challenges in Uganda’s Urban Areas*. Kampala: Makerere University Press.
- 14) Kamulegeya, H., 2017. *The evolution and performance of the real estate sector in Uganda*. Kampala: Uganda Revenue Authority Policy Brief, pp.20–28.
- 15) Keivani, R. and Werna, E., 2001. *Modes of housing provision in developing countries*. *Progress in Planning*, 55(2), pp.65–118.
- 16) Knight Frank Uganda. 2023. *Uganda Property Market Report 2023*. Kampala: Knight Frank.
- 17) Knight Frank, 2019. *Africa Horizons: 2019/20*. Nairobi: Knight Frank Research.
- 18) Kothari, C.R. 2004. *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*. 2nd ed. New Delhi: New Age International Publishers.
- 19) Krejcie M., and Morgan R. 1970. Determining Sample Size for Research Activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 607-610.
- 20) Li, J., Ng, S.T. and Skitmore, M., 2016. *Conflict or consensus: An investigation of stakeholder concerns during the participation process of major infrastructure and construction projects in Hong Kong*. *Habitat International*, 53, pp.78–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.habitatint.2015.11.008>

- 21) Ling, D.C. and Archer, W.R. 2017. *Real estate principles: A value approach*. 5th ed. New York: McGraw-Hill Education, 420.
- 22) Newport International Journal. 2024. *Urbanization and Its Impact on Real Estate Development in Uganda*. Available at: <https://nijournals.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/NIJCIAM-4341-44-2024.pdf> (Accessed 5 October 2025).
- 23) Miles, M.B. and Huberman, A.M. 1994. *Qualitative data analysis: An expanded sourcebook*. 2nd ed. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- 24) Ministry of Finance, Planning and Economic Development. 2024. *Macroeconomic & Fiscal Performance Report Financial Year 2023/24*. Kampala: Ministry of Finance, Planning and Economic Development. Available at: <https://mepd.finance.go.ug/documents/MFP/MFP-FY202324.pdf> (Accessed 5 October 2025).
- 25) Ministry of Finance, Planning and Economic Development. n.d. *Urban development*. [Online]. Available at: <https://development.finance.go.ug/urban-development> (Accessed 5 October 2025).
- 26) MLHUD (2020) *Annual Sector Performance Report 2019/2020*. Kampala: Ministry of Lands, Housing and Urban Development.
- 27) Moyo, S. 2013. *Land and agrarian reform in Zimbabwe: Beyond white-settler capitalism*. CODESRIA.
- 28) MSCI, 2020. *Real Estate Market Size 2020*. London: MSCI Research.
- 29) Mugambwa, J. (2007). *Principles of Land Law in Uganda*. Kampala: Fountain Publishers.
- 30) Oryema, L. M. W. 2016. *A Real Property Register to Support the Property and Credit Market in Uganda*. Doctoral Thesis in Real Estate Planning and Land Law, Royal Institute of Technology (KTH).
- 31) Pagliari, J., 2017. *What do we know about real estate risk and return?*. *Journal of Portfolio Management*, 43(6), pp.12–26.
- 32) Rose-Ackerman, S. 1999. *Corruption and government: Causes, consequences, and reform*. Cambridge University Press.
- 33) Savills, 2021. *World Research: Global Real Estate Value 2021*. London: Savills Research.
- 34) Stanbic Properties Limited. 2022. *Half Year Kampala Metropolitan Real Estate Property Market Report*. Stanbic Bank. Available: https://www.stanbic.co.ug/static_file/Uganda%20Holdings/Downloadable%20files/SPL%20KAMPALA%20METROPOLITAN%20REAL%20ESTATE%20Report%20June%202022.pdf (Accessed 5th March 2025).
- 35) Saunders, M., Lewis, P., and Thornhill, A., 2019. *Research methods for business students*. 8th ed. Harlow: Pearson, p. 157.
- 36) Tashakkori, A. & Teddlie, C. (1998) *Mixed Methodology: Combining Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- 37) Transparency International. 2011. *Global corruption report: Land and corruption*. Transparency International.
- 38) Toulmin, C. and Quan, J. (eds.) (2000) *Evolving Land Rights, Policy and Tenure in Africa*. London: International Institute for Environment and Development (IIED)/Natural Resources Institute. ISBN 1-899825-51-7.
- 39) Uganda Bureau of Statistics (UBOS). 2023. *Statistical Abstract*. Kampala: Available: <https://www.ubos.org/wp-content/uploads/publications/2023-Statistical-Abstract.pdf> (Accessed 3 February 2025).
- 40) Uganda Bureau of Statistics (UBOS) 2021, *Annual business inquiry report*, UBOS, Kampala.

- 41) Uganda Bureau of Statistics (UBOS). 2020. *Statistical Abstract*. Kampala: UBOS, Kampala.
- 42) Uganda Investment Authority (UIA). 2022. *Investor guide to Uganda's real estate sector*. Kampala: UIA. pp.31–33.
- 43) USAID. 2018. *Land Governance Assessment Framework: Uganda Country Report*. Washington DC: USAID. p.22
- 44) UNDP Uganda (2023) *Identifying solutions to Uganda's flooding challenge through community engagement*. Kampala: UNDP. Available at: <https://www.undp.org/uganda/blog/identifying-solutions-ugandas-flooding-challenge-through-community-engagement> (Accessed: 14 March 2025)
- 45) UN-Habitat. 2023. *Uganda Country Brief Final (EN)*. [Online]. Available at: https://unhabitat.org/sites/default/files/2023/07/uganda_country_brief_final_en_1.pdf (Accessed 5 August 2025).
- 46) UN-Habitat. 2015. *The Challenge of Local Government Financing in Developing Countries*. Nairobi: UN-HABITAT. Retrieved November 26, 2021.
- 47) UN-Habitat. (2012). *Handling Land: Innovative Tools for Land Governance and Secure Tenure*. Nairobi: UN-Habitat.
- 48) U4 Anti-Corruption Resource Centre. 2015. *Corruption in land administration: Risks and reform approaches*. Chr. Michelsen Institute.
- 49) World Bank. 2025. *Uganda Overview: Development news, research, data*. [Online]. Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/uganda/overview> (Accessed 3 July 2025).
- 50) World Bank. (2019). *Uganda Economic Update: Developing the Real Estate Sector through Land Reform*. Washington, DC: World Bank.